

PROCEEDINGS OF THE 5TH SESSION OF

INDIAN ART HISTORY CONGRESS

BHUBANESHWAR : FEBRUARY, 1997

Editor
Dr.C.P.Sinha

INDIAN ART HISTORY CONGRESS

GUWAHATI : ASSAM : INDIA

UNDEŚVARA MAHĀDEVA TEMPLE AT BIJOLIAN, RAJASTHAN

B.L.Nagarch *

Bijolian is a tehsil headquarters of Bhilwara district in Rajasthan. It is a Railway station on the Delhi-Bombay main line of Western Rly. and is located 90 km. from Kota on Kota-Udaipur Road passing through Bundi on State high way no.9. Bijolian is 60 km. from Kota via Dabi, 85 km. from Bhilwara and 225 km. from Udaipur. It is a famous for a group of three temples, all dedicated to Śiva- (1) Mahākāleśvar, the main temple, (2) Hajāreśvar temple and (3) Undeśvara temple. All these temples are under the protection of the ASI and are assignable to the 12th century A.D. They were built during the reign of Chāhmānas of Ajmer.

Undeśvara Mahādeva Temple :

The Undeśvara Mahādeva temple follows the plan of the Śiva temple at Ramgarh distt. Kota. However, in elevation this temple shows nine storeys. The temple consists on plan of a *saptaratha* sanctum an *antarāla*, a *sabhāmandapa* with a central hall and three *mukhamandapas* of which two lateral ones have been converted into small chambers. The temple faces west and is approached by a flight of four ascending steps on the western side. The last step is decorated with *chandraśīlā* flanked on either side by a conch.

Sanctum

The sanctum measures 2.45 mt. sq. and enshrines a *Śivalinga* installed on a square *yonipatta* measuring 75 cm. The *Śivalinga* is 0.20 mt. high and has a circumference measuring 0.60mt. on the top. The interior of the sanctum is plain. In the northern wall of the sanctum is a projecting stone lintel for keeping lamp and other articles for worship. There are four ventilators, two in the eastern and one each in the northern and southern walls of the sanctum on the top. The architrave of the ceiling is decorated with two friezes,

* E-121, Sector 27, Noida, Ghaziabad-201302.

Back View of Undesware Mahadeva temple at Bijolian, Rajasthan

Sculpture of dancing Ganesa, Undesuara-Mahadeva Temple Bijolian, Rajasthan.

Interior ceiling of central hall of sabhamandapa undesuara-Mahadeva temple, Bijolian, Rajasthan

Sculptures of Surasundaris, on the Vedika, Undesuara - Temple, Bijolian, Rajasthan

Sculpture of Vaikunthi Sharma, Undesuara Temple, Bijolian, Rajasthan

Door-way of the Sanctum Undesuara-Mahadeva temple, Bijolian, Rajasthan

Sculpture of Karttikeya, Undesuara-Mahadeva Temple, Bijolian, Rajasthan.

Sculptures of female attendants and river goddess Yamuna on the left flank of sancurium doorway, Bijolian, Rajasthan

the lower one showing a *padmalatā* issuing out from a *kirttimukha* in the centre and the upper one decorated with diamonds and rosettes. The ceiling of the sanctum is of *nābhichchanda* variety and is decorated on the top with a full-blown lotus. There is a water-cistern for storing the *abhisheka* water in the south-eastern corner of the sanctum. The floor of the sanctum is 2.35mt. deeper than the doorshell of the sanctum-doorway.

The ceiling above the flight of steps is decorated with two full-blown lotuses and rests on an archtrave carved with a *padmalatā*.

Sanctum-doorway

The sanctum-doorway is decorated with eight *sākhās* of which the first is decorated with lotus-scrolls, the second is carved with *nāgas* in *añjalimudrā*, the third is embellished with spiral lotus-scrolls and *padmalatā*. The fourth depicts Champāka flowers. The fifth is a *rūpastambha* decorated with vase-and-foilage-motif, the seventh is carved with *kārnikā* moulding while the eighth portrays lotus petals. The *lalātabimba* shows four armed Śiva seated in *padamāsana* and carrying *varada*, *trisūla*, *sarpa* and *kamandalu*. The lower portions of the *sākhā* portray the river goddess Gaṅgā on the right and Yamunā on the left carrying *Kalaśa* and *Kaṭi*, three female attendants each standing in *tribhaṅga* and two of them carrying *chaurī* and *Kaṭi*. One of the female attendants carries a flower bud. The niche in the lower portion of the *rūpastambha* shows a four-armed Śaiva *dvārapālas* standing in *tribhaṅga*, the one on the right carrying *khatvaṅga*, *damaru*, *sarpa* and *kapāla* and the other on the left carrying *varada*, *damaru*, *trisūla* and a *padma*. The seated mount bull is carved on the side. The sixth *sākhā* shows on the lower portion two-armed Kubera standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a purse held by his both hands. The door-sill shows in the centre a *mandāraka* consisting of bold lotus-stalks and flanked on either side by a bold *kirttimukha*. Below the *sākhās* on the right flank of the sanctum-doorway are shown three female attendants each standing in *tribhaṅga* and a four-armed male deity seated in *lalitāsana*, four-armed Śiva seated in *lalitāsana* inside a niche, a female attendant and a four-armed male deity seated in *lalitāsana*. Below the *sākhā* on the left flank of the sanctum-doorway are shown three female attendants each standing in *tribhaṅga*, four-armed Brahmā seated in *lalitāsana* inside a niche, four-armed Śiva seated in *lalitāsana* inside a niche flanked on either side by a standing female *chaurī* bearer and four armed Viṣṇu seated in *lalitāsana*. The sanctum door-way measures 1.95mt. high, .092 mt. broad and .22 mt. thick.

Antarāla

The *antarāla* measures 0.25 mt. long and 2.65mt. broad. In front of the door-sill is seen a *chandrasilā* flanked on either side by a conch.

Sabhāmandapa

The *Sabhāmandapa* measures 7.10 mt. sq. There is a parapet wall on all the four sides of the *Sabhāmandapa* which is surmounted by a *āsanapaṭṭa*. Above the *āsanapaṭṭa* is fixed *kakṣāsana*. There is a central hall in the centre of the *Sabhāmandapa* which measures 3.50 mt. long and 3.85 mt. broad. The ceiling of the central hall rests on four pillars, one at each of the four corners. These pillars are similar in design and ornamentation. However, they differ in showing images of deities and *surasundarīs*. Each of these pillars shows a *khura* decorated with a frieze of diamonds, *kumbha* decorated with a niche containing an image of seated deity on each of the four faces, *kalasa* and *kapota* decorated with *kuṇḍus*. Above this rests the shaft which is square in the lower portion, octagonal and sixteen-sided in the middle portion and circular on the top. The square portion of the shaft shows a niche on each of the four faces containing an image of a deity or an ascetic and *surasundarī*. The circular portion of the shaft is decorated with an octagonal band of *kīrttimukhas* surmounted by a half diamond design. Above the shaft rests the capital consisting of a *karnikā* and a *padma* and surmounted by flying *bhūta* brackets. Above these brackets rests the sur-capital which supports brackets with a single volute. The bracket supports the decorated architrave of the ceiling carved with three friezes. Above the architrave rests the ceiling of *nābhichchhanda* variety which is decorated at the bottom with eight brackets showing four-armed flying *bhūtas* carrying different attributes such as sword, and shield by their hands. The central hall is decorated with four *makaratoranas* of which the one on the eastern side is missing. This is a noteworthy feature of the central hall of this *Sabhāmandapa*.

Pillars of Central Hall of Sabhāmandapa

- A. *South-eastern pillar* : The *kumbha* moulding of the base of the pillar shows seated Brāhmī, Pārvatī, Vaiṣṇavī and Māheshvarī inside four niches. The niches on the lower portion of the shaft of the pillar show (1) a bearded Sādhu standing in *tribhaṅga* in *āñjalimudrā*. His *jatājūṭa* is seen above his head. His *kamaṇḍalu* is tied on his left shoulder. His left leg has been chopped off. (2) A *Surasundarī* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a *śāṅkha* and *kaṭi*. She wears the *dhammilla*

type of head-dress, *kunḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, a scarf and a *sārī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. A flower bud is kept on her right. (3) A *surasundarī* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a lotus-stalk by her left hand, her right hand is upraised above her head. A flower pot is kept on her right. (4) A male drummer standing in *tribhaṅga* and beating a drum.

B. *South-western pillar* : The *kumbha* moulding of this pillar shows four niches containing images of seated *Brāhmī*, *Vaiṣṇavī*, *Māheshvarī* and *Pārvaṭī*. The lotus-portion of this shaft shows inside a niche : (1) A *surasundarī* drenching her hair held by her left hand. Her right hand is placed on her left breast. She is half dressed. (2) A *surasundarī* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a conch and *kaṭi*. Two armed *kūberi* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a purse by her both hands. (3) Two-armed Bhairava standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a small dagger and a *kapāla*. Above his head is a serpent-canopy and he wears *kunḍalas*, *sarpa-hāra* and *sarpa-mekhalā*. He is shown naked. A scarf is seen hanging from his shoulder.

C. *North-western Pillar* : The *kumbha* moulding of the base of the pillar shows four niches containing seated *Vaiṣṇavī*, seated *Brāhmī*, seated *Pārvaṭī* and seated *Mātrikā* whose attributes have been chopped off. The four niches in the lower portion of the shaft show (1) Two-armed Bhairava standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a small dagger and *kapāla*. He wears dress and ornaments similar to the Bhairava on the south-western pillar. (2) A *surasundarī* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a *śaṅkha* and *kaṭi*, (3) A *Surasundarī* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a *kapāla* and a *daṇḍa* (4) A dancing *surasundarī* with her leg folded at the knee and upraised.

D. *North-eastern Pillar* : The four niches on the *kumbha* moulding on the base of the pillar contain images of seated four-armed *Brāhmī*, *Kauberī*, *Kaumārī* and *Māheshvarī*. The niches in the lower portion of the shaft of this pillar show. (1) a male-drummer standing in *tribhaṅga* and beating a drum (2) a bearded male (*śaivāchārya*) standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *varadāksha* and *pustaka*. (3) A *Surasundarī* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a *kaṭi* and *śaṅkha* (4) two-armed Kubera standing in *tribhaṅga* and holding a purse by his both hands. At present a seated *Nandī* is kept inside the central hall of the *Sabhāmandapa*. He has a prominent hump and wears a chain of bells around his neck. It measures

50 cm. x 20 cm. x 35 cm. It is a loose sculpture and is of later period than the temple. The ceiling of the *Sabhāmandapa* rests on ten dwarf pillars, five on each side, besides the four pillars of the central hall and two pilasters attached near the sanctum-doorway. Each of the dwarf pillars shows a base decorated with stencilled lotus-scrolls, *kīrtīmukhas*, a *haṅśa mithuna* and lotus medallion. The lower portion of the shaft is decorated with *ghaṭapallava* motif. The upper portion of the shaft is circular and is decorated with a band of diamonds and rosettes. The shaft supports a circular capital consisting of a *karnikā* and *padma* and is surmounted by flying *bhūta* brackets. The *bhūta* brackets support the decorated architrave of the ceiling showing five friezes carved with stencilled lotus-scrolls issuing out of *kīrtīmukhas*, diamonds and rosettes, niches containing the images of seated deities and diamonds in panels. The architrave supports the ceiling of the *nābhichchanda* variety consisting of thirteen bands of overlapping concentric circles. The top of the ceiling is decorated with a lotus motif. The pilasters attached near the sanctum-doorway show on the base a niche containing an image of a bearded ascetic standing in *tribhaṅga* and two niches containing an image of Viṣṇu and Śiva on the right and Aindrī and Māheshvarī on the left. The upper portion of the shaft is decorated with a band of *kīrtīmukhas*. The shaft supports a capital consisting of a *karnikā* and *padma* above which rest the flying *bhūta* brackets.

The lateral *mukhamandapas* of the *sabhāmandapa* show a shrine-chamber measuring 2.20 mt. sq. The doorway of each of the chambers measures 1 mt. high, 0.55 mt. broad and 0.25 mt. thick. The door-way is decorated with two plain *sākhās* and shows a diamond inside the panels in the lower portion of the *sākhās*. The door-sill is decorated with a lotus in the centre flanked on either side by another lotus. The ceiling of each of the lateral *mukhamandapas* rests on four dwarf pillars each being similar in design and ornamentation. Above this pillar rest the flying *bhūta*-brackets supporting the decorated architrave of the ceiling carved with two friezes, one showing lotus-scrolls issuing out of a *kīrtīmukha* and the other showing diamonds and rosettes. The architrave supports a ceiling of *nābhichchanda* variety decorated with seven bands of concentric overlapping circles and *kolā* and *gajataḷu* courses.

Ardhamandapa

The *ardhamandapa* measures 4.70 mt. long and 2.60 mt. broad. There is a

parapet wall on the northern and southern sides of the *ardhamandapa* which is surmounted by *āsanapaṭṭa*. The *kakshasana* which rested on the *āsanapaṭṭa* is missing as evident from the sockets in the *āsanapaṭṭa*. Above the *āsanapaṭṭa* rest the four dwarf pillars similar in ornamentation and design to the other dwarf pillars similar in ornamentation and design to the other dwarf pillars of the *mukhamandapas* on the southern and northern sides. These pillars support flying *bhūta*-brackets which are surmounted by decorated architrave of the ceiling carved with two friezes showing stencilled lotus-scrolls issuing out of *kīrtīmukha* and a band of diamonds and rosettes. Above this are shown niches containing images of seated deities and surmounted by a frieze of diamonds in panels. The architrave supports the *nābhichchanda* variety of the ceiling consisting of eight bands of overlapping concentric circles and decorated with *kola* and *gajātālu* courses. On the lower portion of the ceiling are shown eight flying *bhūta*-brackets which support the ceiling. At each of the four corners of the ceiling is carved a *kīrtīmukha*. There are two niches on the western side of the *ardhamandapa* flanking the steps. The niches on the northern wall contains an image of eight armed *kārtikeya* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *śakti* and *kamaṇḍalu* by his only surviving two hands. His remaining hands have been chopped off. He wears *jaṭāmukuta*, *kundalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *valayas*, *keyūras*, *nūpurās*, a long *mālā* and a *dhotī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. The seated mount peacock is shown behind him

The niche on the southern wall contains an image of dancing *Gaṇeśa* carrying *nrityamudrā*, *sarpa*, *modakapātra* and a *kalasā*. He wears *kirīṭāmukuta*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *nūpurās*, a long *mālā* and a *dhotī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. A male-drummer on his left while the mount mouse is shown on his right. It may be noted that there is an inscription of two lines in Sanskrit language and devanāgarī character which is dated VS 1218. On the pedestal of the bearded ascetic shown on the lower portion of the shaft of one of the pilasters of *sabhāmandapa*. From the inscriptions it is evident that the temple was constructed in 12th cent. A. D.

The Roof of The Ardhamandapa:

The roof of the *ardhamandapa* shows a *kūṭachchāḍya* resting on the brackets in the parapet wall decorated on the western side with six niches. The niches from left to right show (1) four-armed dancing *Gaṇeśa* whose trunk and right leg have been chopped off. (2) four-armed *Viṣṇu* seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *varada*, *gadā*, *padma* and *śaṅkha*.

He wears a *kirītamukūṭa*, *kundālas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *keyū ras*, *valayas*, *nūpurās*, and a *dhōṭī* fastened by a *mekhalā*. The niche is flanked on either side by a female *chaurī*-bearer standing in *tribhaṅga* (3) a niche containing a diamond design (4) a niche containing four-armed *Vaiṣṇavī* seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *varada*, *gadāchakṛa* and *śāṅkha*. She is flanked on either side by a female *chaurī*-bearer standing in *tribhaṅga*. (6) A niche containing an image of four-armed dancing *mātrikā* probably *Māheshvarī*. Her *jaṭāmukūṭa* and all of her hands have been chopped off and also her right leg and breasts. The roof of the *ardhamandapa* is flat and supports a pillared kiosk crowned by a *sālāsikhara* decorated on the top with double *kalasā* and *bījapūraka*.

Elevation

The *ardhamandapa* and the two *mukhamandapas* show in elevation from bottom upwards *pīṭha* mouldings consisting from bottom upwards of a plain *paṭṭikā jālyakumbha*, *karnikā paṭṭikā*, a *grasa paṭṭi gajathara*, *rājasena* decorated with diamonds, in panels *vedikā* or pilasters decorated with foliage and *śāṅkha* and dancing and standing *surasundarī*s inside the recesses, and *kakshāsana* decorated with foliage. There are niches at the corners of the *vedikā* which contain images of standing or dancing deities. Starting from northwest corner, the niches show:

- (1) Four armed Varuṇa standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *varadāksha* pāśa lotus- stalk and *kalasā*. The seated mount *makara* is shown on his left. Varuṇa wears *kirīttamukūṭa* *kundālas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *nūpurās*, a long *mālā* and a *dhōṭī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels.
- (2) Ten-armed Narasimha ripping open the belly of the demon Hiranyakāśpū by his two hands. He has the head of a lion and all of his hands have been chopped off. The seated mount *garuḍa* in *añjalimudrā* is shown on his right while a male attendant standing in *tribhaṅga* is shown on his left.
- (2A) A chopped niche is lying vacant.
- (3) Eight-armed Śiva or Natarāja is seen dancing. He carries a *damaru*, *sarpa*, *kapāla* and *nrityamudrā* by his surviving hands. His remaining three hands have been chopped off. He wears *jaṭāmukūṭa*, *kundālas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *nūpurās*, a long *mālā* and a *dhōṭī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. The seated mount bull is shown on his left

while a male drummer is seen on his right.

- (4) four-armed Vāyu standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *varadāksha*, *dhvaja*, and *kamaṇḍalu*. He wears usual dress and ornaments. The leaping mount deer is shown on his right.
- (5) A four-armed deity standing in *samapāda* and carrying a *pustaka* by his only surviving upper left hand. He wears *karandamukuta*, *kunḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *nūpuras*, a long *mālā* and a *dhōṭī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. The seated mount which appears to be a *hamsa*, is shown on his left.
- (6) A niche containing an image of eight-armed devī (vaikunṭhī) standing in *tribhaṅga*. She has three heads. The central head is that of a horse while the head on the right is that of a lion and the head on the left is that of varāha. She wears *karandamukuta*, *kunḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *nūpuras*, a long *mālā* and a *dhōṭī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. She carries *varadāksha* and *kapāla* by her only surviving two hands. The standing mount lion shown on her right and a *agnikunḍa* is shown on her left.
- (7) A niche containing an image of four-armed Harihara standing in *samapāda* and carrying a *trisūla* by his upper right hand and a *śaṅkha* by his lower left hand. His lower right hand and upper left hand have been chopped off. He wears *jatāmukuta* on the right half of his head and a *kirīttamukuta* on the left half of his head, *kunḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, a long *mālā* and a *dhōṭī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. The seated mount bull with his upraised head, is shown on his right.
- (8) Four-armed Ardhanārīśvara standing in *samapāda* and carrying a *trisūla* by his upper right hand, a spiral lotus-stalk containing Geṇeśa by his upper left hand and chopped *kalasā*. He wears *jatāmukuta*, *kunḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *nūpuras*, a long *mālā* and a *dhōṭī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. His right half is that of Śiva and left half is that of Umā. The seated mount bull is shown on his right.
- (9) Four-armed Kubera standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a chopped *gadā* and purse. He wears a *karandamukuta*, *kunḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*,

keyūras, *valayas*, *nūpurās*, a long *mālā* and a *dhōṭī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. Both of his lower hands and right leg have been chopped off. The standing mount elephant is shown on his left.

- 10) Four-armed Śiva or Īśāna standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying chopped off, *trisūla*, *sarpa* and *kalasā*. He wears usual dress and ornaments. The seated mount bull with upraised head is shown on his right.

The niches on the *vedikā* on the southern side *mukhamandāpa* and *ardhamandāpa* contain the following sculptures:

- (1) Four-armed Indra standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a *vajra* by his upper right hand and a *kalasā* by his lower left hand. His lower right hand and upper left hand have been chopped off. He wears usual dress and ornaments. The seated mount elephant is shown in his left.
- (2) Four-armed Agni standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *varadāksha*, *sruk*, spiral lotus-stalk and chopped off. He is bearded and wears usual drapery and ornaments. The standing mount ram, whose head has been chopped off is shown on his right.
- (3) A chopped niche, the pedestal of which is carved with a frieze of diamonds and rosettes has survived.
- (4) Four-armed Sūrya standing in *samapāda* and wearing *kirīttamukuta*, *kundalas*, *vaiśakshyaka*, *kavacha*, *yajñopavīta*, *keyūras*, a long *mālā* long boots and a *dhōṭī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. All of his hands have been chopped off. The seated animal mount whose hind and fore legs have been chopped off, is shown on his right. The sculpture measures 0.75mt x 0.50mt x 0.15mt.
- (5) Four-armed Vāmana standing in *samapāda* and carrying a *pustaka* by his upper right hand and a *chhatra* by his upper left hand. Both of his left hands have been chopped off. He has matted hair locks on his head and wears usual drapery and ornaments.
- (6) Six-armed Śarasvatī standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a *vīṇā* by her right hands. She wears usual drapery and ornaments. The seated mount swan is shown on her right.
- (7) A chopped niche.

- (8) Four-armed Viṣṇu standing in *samapāda*. He wears usual drapery and ornaments. All of his hands have been chopped off. The flying mount Garuḍa in *añjalimudrā* is shown on his left.
- (9) A completely chopped niche.
- (10) A niche containing an image of four-armed Yama standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *varadāksha* chopped off, *kukkūṭa* and *kalasā*. He wears usual drapery and ornaments. The seated mount buffalo is shown on his left.
- (11) Four-armed Nirriti standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a small dagger, *damaru khetaka* and chopped off. he wears a head dress of serpent-hoods, *sarpa-kunḍalas*, *sarpa-hara*, *nīpuras*, a long *mālā* and a *mekhalā*. He is shown naked. The animal mount on his left appears to be a lion with chopped head.
- (12) A chopped niche.
- (13) Four-armed dancing Bhairava carrying a small dagger, *damaru*, *kapḍa* and *munḍa*. He wears a head dress of serpent-hoods, *kunḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *pādukas*, a long *mālā* and a *dhoī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. He is shown bearded and has long moustaches.

Surasundarīs inside the recess of the *vedikā* of *ardhamandapa* and *mukhamandapas*. The *surasundarīs* are shown in various postures such as standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying lotus-stalk and *kaṭi*, dancing, yawning, disrobing, holding her breasts and carrying *chaurī*. Besides *surasundarīs*, ascetics standing in *anjanimudra* and amorous couples are also shown inside the recesses. One of the *surasundarīs* is seen showing her organ while another *Surasundarī* is shown drenching her hair. A male drummer is also shown inside the recess.

Roof of the northern and southern mukhamandapas

These roofs show a *kuṭachhāya* resting on a decorated architrave of the ceiling, a plain *antarpatra* and a parapet wall decorated with diamonds in panels. The roofs on both the *mukha-mandapas* are flat and support a domed pillared kiosk, probably build during the Maratha period. The parapet wall of the roof of the southern *mukhamandapa* also shows a *chaitya dormer* decorated on the borders with mongo-strings and lotus-scrolls and four niches containing images of deities. From left to right the niches show (1) a dancing *mārikā* whose lower two hands and both the legs have been chopped off. She

carries a *chakra* by her upper right hand. (2) Four-armed dancing *Māheshvarī* carrying *varada*, chopped off, lotus-stalk and *kamṇḍalu*. (3) A niche containing an image of four-armed Śiva seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *varadāksha*, *triśūla*, *sarpa* and *kamaṇḍalu*. The niche is flanked on either side by a female *chaurī*-bearer. (4) A niche containing an image of four-armed Aindri seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *varada*, *aṅkusa*, *vajra* and *kamaṇḍalu*. It is flanked on either side by a female *chaurī*-bearer standing in *tribhāṅga*.

In elevation the sanctum shows *pīṭha* mouldings which are in common with the *mukhamandāpas* upto *gajathara*. Above this the sanctum shows a plain *khura*, *karnīkā kumbha* decorated on the top with lotus-petals, a median band of diamonds and rosettes and niches containing the images of seated deities, plain *antarpatra*, *kalasā* decorated with diamonds and rosettes, plain *antarpatra*, *kapota* decorated with *kudūs* and *mañchikā* decorated with typical *chaitya*-arches of Paramara style. These mouldings constitute the *adhishthāna* which supports the *jaṅghā* decorated with a single register of sculptures. Starting from the northwest corner, the sculptures on the *jaṅghā* are as follows:

- (1) A niche on the *antarāla* containing an image of ten armed *Chāmundā* carrying a *damaru*, *triśūla*, and *sarpa* by her only surviving three right hands and *sarpa khatvāṅga* and *kapāla* by her only surviving left hands. She wears *jaṭāmukuta*, *kuṇḍalas*, *muṇḍamālā* and *sari* fastened a *mekhalā*. She has drooping breasts and emaciated body in the form of skeleton. A *sarpa* is seen on her belly. Her five hands, and both the legs have been chopped off. The mount corpse is shown on the right. She is flanked on the right by a male goblin carrying a small dagger. A seated male devotee on her right is seen playing with her mount lion.
- (2) Four-armed Varuṇa standing in *tribhāṅga* and carrying *varadāksha*, *pāśa*, spiral lotus-stalk and *kalasā*. he wears usual drapery and ornaments. The seated mount crocodile is seen on his left.
- (3) Four-armed Vāyu standing in *tribhāṅga* and carrying *varadāksha*, banner, hammer and *kamaṇḍalu*.
- (4) A surasundari in the act of wearing a nupura held by his both the hands in her uplifted right leg.
- (5) A *Surasundarī* standing front back and playing on flute.

- (6) A *Surasundarī* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a *sarpa* by her left hand. Her right hand is uplifter near her head.
- (7) A *Surasundarī* standing in *tribhaṅga* and yawning.
- (8) A niche on the northern *bhādra* of the sanctum containing an image of six-armed flying Garuḍa carrying a *chakra* by his only surviving lower right hand and *padma*, *sarpa* and *śaṅkha* by his left hands.
- (9) A yogini standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a *kapāla* and a *chakra* by her right and left hands. She is shown naked. She wears *vaikakshyaka*, a *vastra*, *yajñopavīta*, *rudrāksha*, *keyūras* and *rudrāksha-valayas*.
- (10) Two-armed Nirriti standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *khadga*, and *munda* by his right and left hands. He is bearded and moustached. He wears a head-dress of serpent-hoods, *kundalas*, *sarpa*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *nīpurās*, a long *mālā*. He is shown naked. The mount lion is shown on his left.
- (11) A two-armed Devī standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying an arrow by her right hand and bow by her left hand. She wears *karandamukuta*, *kundalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *nīpurās*, scarf and a *sārī* fastened by a *mekhālā* with loops and tassels. His-standing animal mount, which appears to be a bull, is shown on her left.
- (12) A four-armed naked Devī standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a small dagger, *damaru*, *kapāla* and a *munda*. She is Bhairavī and wears a head dress of a serpent-hoods *kundalas*, *vastra*, *yajñopavīta*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *nīpurās*, a long *mālā*. The mount dog with upraised head is shown on her left.
- (13) Four-armed Kubera standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *gadā*, purse and *kamaṇḍalu*. He wears usual drapery and ornaments. His seated mount elephant is shown on his left.
- (14) Four-armed Īśāna standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *varadāksha*, *trisūta*, *sarpa*, and *kamaṇḍalu*. The seated mount bull is shown on his left.
- (15) A dancing *surasundarī*.
- (16) A bearded male drummer beating a drum.
- (17) A dancing *surasundarī*.
- (18) A male drummer playing on a drum.
- (19) A niche on the eastern *bhādra* of the sanctum containing an image of four-

armed Brahmā seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *varadāksha*, chopped off, *pustaka* and *kamaṇḍalu*. He is bearded and wears *jaṭāmukuta*, *kunḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *yajñopavita*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *nūpurās* and *dhotī* fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. He is three headed.

- (20) A *Surasundarī* standing in *tribhaṅga* and yawning.
- (21) A lady in toilet drenching her hair held by her right hand.
- (22) A *Surasundarī* playing on a drum.
- (23) A male drummer playing on a drum.
- (24) Four-armed Indra standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *varadāksha*, *vajra*, *aṅkusa* and *kamaṇḍalu*. The seated mount elephant is shown on his right.
- (25) Four-armed Agni standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *vardāksha*, *sruk*, *pustaka* and *kamaṇḍalu*.
- (26) A *Surasundarī* standing in *tribhaṅga* and yawning.
- (27) A *Surasundarī* playing on a drum.
- (28) A *Surasundarī* playing with a ball held by her uplifted right hand.
- (29) A *Surasundarī* disrobing herself.
- (30) A niche on the southern *bhadra* containing an image of four-armed Viṣṇu seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *varadāksha*, *gadā*, *chakra* and chopped off.
- (31) A dancing *surasundarī*. Her right hand is uplifted near her head and she holds a flower by her left hand.
- (32) A *Surasundarī* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying a *kalasā* and *kaṭi*.
- (33) A dancing *Surasundarī*.
- (34) A *Surasundarī* is seen disrobing herself.
- (35) Four-armed yama standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *varadāksha*, chopped *khaṭvāṅga*, *kukkuta* and *kamaṇḍalu*. The seated mount buffalo is seen on the left.
- (36) Two-armed Chamuṇḍā seated in *utkūṭekāsana* on a cot. She has two arms and has ferocious look with bulging eyes and protruding teeth. She wears *sarpa*, *kunḍalas* and *Sarpa-vaikakshyaka*. A scorpion is seen on her belly. She is shown naked. Both of her hands and legs have been chopped off. This sculpture is important from the iconographic point of view and is a rare sculp-

ture of Chāmuṇḍā. She is shown with drooping breasts and emaciated body in the form of the skeleton. This niche is shown on the southern wall of the *antarāla*.

It may be noted that besides the sculptures on the *bhadras* inside niches and on the projections, the recesses of the *janghā* contained pilaster designs surmounted by a shrine motif, and diamonds in panels. This feature is common with the Māmleśvara temple at *Onkāreśvara* in distt. Khandwa (M.P.). There are two holes in the walls of the sanctum on either side of the three *bhadras* for admitting light and air. However, this arrangement is not sufficient and the sanctum remains comparatively dark.

The niches on the *kumbha* mouldings of the *adhishthāna* contain seated images of Vaināyikī, Kubera, Brahmā, Śiva Pārvatī, Vaiṣṇavī, Māheshvarī, Kaumārī and Chāmuṇḍā.

The *janghā* supports the *varaṇḍikā* mouldings consisting of a *kūttachhādyā* and a *kapota* decorated with *kudus*. Above the *varaṇḍikā* rests the nine storied *sikhara* filled with nine horizontal and five vertical rows of miniature shrine models in the quadrants. The *mūlamanjarī* of the *sapta ratha sikhara* is decorated with a mesh of *chaitya*-arches and shows at the bottom on all the four sides a large *chaitya*-dormer crowned by a *kīrttimukha* and containing an image of dancing Śiva or Natarāja. Below the *chaitya*-dormers on all the four sides, are niches containing images of seated deities. There is a niche on the *antarāla* also containing an image. The niche in the northern wall of the *antarāla* contains an image of four *Andhakāsuravadhamurti* of Śiva, while the niche in the southern wall of the *antarāla* contains an image of four-armed Viṣṇu seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *abhaya*, *śaṅkha*, *chakra* and *kalāśa*. The niches on the northern side of the *sikhara* show :

- (1) Four-armed Brahmā seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *varadāksha*.
- (2) Four-armed Brahmā standing in *samapāda* and carrying *varada*, *sruk*, *pustaka* and *kamaṇḍalu*. He is bearded and single headed.

The niche on the eastern side of the *sikhara* contains :

- (1) An image of four-armed Śiva seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *varada*, *triśūla*, *śarpa* and *kamaṇḍalu*.
- (2) A standing image of four-armed Devī whose head and both the lower hands have been chopped off.

The niches on the northern side contain an image of (1) four-armed Viṣṇu seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *śaṅkha*, *padma*, *gadā* and *chakra*. His head has been chopped off. The niche is flanked on either side by two female *chaurī*-bearer standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *kaṭi* and *chaurī*s. (2) A niche containing an image of a female *chaurī*-bearer standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *kaṭi* and *chaurī*. The *śikhara* is crowned by an *āmalaka*, *chandrikā*, *kalāśa* and *bījapūraka*.

The Roof of Sabhamandapa

The roof of *sabhāmandapa* is of *saṁvarṇa* variety and is decorated with *kūṭtaghaṅṭās*. The upper portion of the roof has been restored by conservation work. There is a *kunḍa* on the southern side of the temple. It is also contemporary with the temple.

2. General Features of the Architectural style

The Uṇḍeśvara Mahādeva temple shares the date and plan of the Śiva temple at Ramgarh, but it is nine-storeyed in elevation. The temple is stellate and *saptaratha* on plan. The *pīṭha* of the temple stands on a pair of *bhittas* and is crowned by the *gajapīṭha*. It is, more substantial than that of Siddheśvara temple at Namawara distt. Dewas (M.P.) It is due to this *pīṭha* that the lower structure does not look stunted. The first two *bhūmis* of the *śikhara* of this temple do not have the full complement of *kūṭtastambhas* but have only *stambhas*. This feature reduces the disparity between the heights of the superstructure and the lower structure. The other notable architectural feature of this temple, is that it has decorative miniature replicas of *Venukośas* on the flanks of the central *latā*. The *sūrasenakas* on the *śikhara* are crowned by *grāsamukhas* and are small but prominent. They contain sculptures. The *latās* have an excessive curvature and taper and are crowned by the triple-head of Śiva as Maheśamūrti. The temple is comparable with the Siddheśvara temple at Nemawar distt. Dewas (M.P.) which is the other known example of *navabhumaprasāda*.

Sculptural art and iconography

The sculptures of the Uṇḍeśvara Mahādeva temple comprise *dikpālas*, *surasundaris*, Chamuṇḍā, Garuḍa, yoginī, other female deities, Brahmā and male-drummers, seated Brāhmī, Pārvatī, Vaiṣṇavī and Māheshvarī Kubera, Bhairava, Narasimha, dancing Śiva or Natarāja, Harihara, Ardhanārīśvara, Sūrya, Vāmana, Śarasvatī, Viṣṇu, seated Śiva and mātrikā Aindri. Thus, we have in this temple the four broad categories

of sculptures, the cult images, the *parivāra devatās*, *surasundarīs* and secular sculptures of music.

The sculptural art of Uṇḍeśvara Mahādeva temple is medieval. The art has surprising human vitality. The modelling of the sculptures has been very beautifully done. The sculptures are comparable with Khajuraho temple sculptures. These sculptures are proportionate and expressive. The sculptures are shown in various moods and fancies. The female sculptures show lovely attributes and postures.

The images of the temple are of great iconographic interest. As the temple is dedicated to Śiva, we have here predominance of Śiva images.

Conclusion :

It may be concluded that Uṇḍeśvara Mahādeva temple occupies an important place among the *bhumija* temples of India. It is iconographically very rich. Here we have the important sculptures of Siva in various forms, such as Naṭarāja, Harihara, Ardhanārīśvara, and Andhakāsuravadhamurti. Besides, we find representations of Viṣṇu, Brahmā, Sūrya, Bhairava, Gaṇeśa, Mātrikās, Kārttikeya, Saivāchāryas, Surasundaris, Dikāpālas, Garuḍas and male-drummers. Among the rare sculptures shown on the walls of the temple are those of standing Vaikuṅṭha and Chāmuṇḍa seated in utkutikāsana. There is a harmonious sculpture and architecture in this temple. The temple is a grand specimen of temple architecture of the Chāhamānas of Ajmer during the twelfth century.

REFERENCE :

1. Krishna Deva, *Temples of North India*, New Delhi, 1969, p.69; Bhumija temples, published in *Studies in Indian temple architecture*, edited by Pramod Chandra, New Delhi, 1975, pp. 106-7, Plate 42.
2. R.C.Agrawala, *A Rare Devi icon from Rajasthan*, Published in *Kala the Journal of Indian Art History Congress*. Vol. II, 1995-96, pp. 4-9, fig. 5.